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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, my name is Anna Makaruke and I'm a student at Bleking Institute of Technology pursuing a Masters in Software Engineering. I'm conducting a research to investigate how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in the open source software dependencies they include in their projects. And this is based on the background that supply chain attacks have become more frequent in recent years and therefore understanding how developers are aware of the risk links to having vulnerable dependencies and dependencies is vital for the open source community as well as the global software development community that relies on these dependencies. So participation in this research is entirely voluntary and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. You will not retain any personnel data or identifiable information. The name, role, e-mail address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone.

You can skip any questions you are not comfortable answering. Your responses will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the projects that you represent. And then the interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the reported data, after which they will be deleted.

So before we start, please introduce yourself and the project, which you are either a developer, contributor, or maintainer. You can mention your role, what you do in the project, and also your job title, how many experience you have in the software development industry, how many years of experience you have with the web framework. And the web frameworks we are focusing on five, so it can be either Django, spring boot, next to JS, Laravel, and Ruby on Rails.

So you should identify which ecosystem you're coming from based on those web frameworks.

Speaker 2

Okay, thank you. Quick question before I go. So first thing, I'm a developer. I'm a software developer. I work for a public organization for the UK. Yeah. So if I mentioned the project.

Okay. All right. Okay. I work for a public, public institution, public entity. It's the project that I'm working on. It's the careers. I manage, I maintain the careers website or system. So the application, generally what it does, I should say the recruitment application. Okay, for this one, I think you can focus on the web framework that you're using.

Okay, I use Spring, I work with Java and Spring. So yeah, that's what I meant.

Speaker 1

How many years of experience do you have with Java?

Speaker 2

Hmm, good question. I think I can say eight years now. It's eight years with Spring, with Spring Boot, then Java. I've been using Java for, I think, 10 years now. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you.

Speaker 2

10 or 12 years. Yeah.

00:03:54 Speaker 1

All right.

Speaker 1

Okay, so which other ecosystems does your project rely on? For example, do you use dependencies? Do you use anything from maybe Python, Java, JavaScript, PHP or Ruby? now within the dependence from those ecosystems in your project.

Speaker 2

I would say. I work on the back end, which is mainly Java and and which is just Java Spring. But the front end is is Javascript. I think Express. And yeah. We, however, use, we have dependencies that we use. Some are our own. and some could be external. Might not too sure what what the what what was used to build them, because I just use it as a dependency that that I just plug in. Sometimes AWS stuff. Yeah. that's what I can say with those ones.

Speaker 1

Hmn. And how are security issue reports managed in your project?

Speaker 2

Oh, yeah. So everyone is responsible for security within the project, everyone who's working on the project. So we have a playbook that we have that we have to follow. And so it's published for everyone. And whether you're writing code, just have to make sure you're taking care of all the vulnerabilities that could be there. And yeah, back to the external dependencies that you mentioned, my role as a developer is to make sure that I keep my dependencies up to date. You know, they get updated and stuff. So There is a temptation or it's a possibility of just if it's working, you don't just don't touch it. But then there's some attacks that are there, some vulnerabilities that are addressed within some updates. So you have got to upgrade and update the dependencies that you are. This is the role of me as a developer. I have to make sure that the dependencies that I'm using are up to date. And so make sure that we are working with updated stuff, updated dependencies.

And there's also, to protect our systems, we are on cloud. I think we're both on cloud and hybrid. But for example, on cloud or cloud systems, we use AWS. Some use Azure. I'm not sure who does, but we use AWS. So together with the infrastructure guys. And the solutions architects. We have to make sure that. We We maintain. Our code and our dependencies. And our rules and we update our rules, for example. We update the-- what is it called? The firewalls.

And I think it's called the WAF. Sorry, let me just quickly-- not the meaning. So yeah, web application firewall. So we have put rules that we put in there. Just to give an example, I was recently working on we're getting too too many requests on on the application from bots. So when both send in too many requests, if they they get like 2 higher amounts of requests that may result in the system being overwhelmed. and some of you might end up getting the the is it the the Dds attacks? You know all those things. Yeah, so yeah, denial service. So when you have all those attacks, to avoid getting those attacks, getting to the actual system, you put in place those firewalls, the rules, and so that we can identify if it's a bot, try to limit the rules.

So that's all the things that we do. Then there are some attacks like whenever there's a new attack that is coming, a message calls organisation-wide. everyone to be aware of it. And sometimes we heard we hold meetings to make sure that everyone is aware of that vulnerability or that attack, and how to be how to prepare for that. Yeah, that's that's what we do.

Speaker 1

And I You mentioned denial sets attacks, but I'm more interested in knowing how aware you are of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects, especially the risks that dependencies you have in your dependency trees create in relation to supply chain threats.

Speaker 2

Okay. Yeah, so. Whenever we're introducing a dependence, we try and it has got to be approved. We have got a set of rules, set of standards on the dependence that are allowed. So they are vetted by the security team. We just don't take any because some are just advertise as to some of them, some dependencies come as Trojan horses. So to try and avoid that, they are still a set of approved, you know, dependencies.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Okay, before I go to my next question, I just want to ask a follow up. You have a security team, or you said every developer is responsible for security, but you do have a security team responsible for overseeing everything.

Speaker 2

Yes. All right. Yes, there are the cybersecurity team within the organization. It's quite a very big organization because I think over 200 developers, only developers. Then there are other technical architects, then there are other solutions architects, and there's a cybersecurity team and testers and all those. But everyone is responsible for security because the cybersecurity team is responsible for the overall security of all the applications. But you as a developer, you need to be aware and you need to take care of the security.

Speaker 1

And how do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your projects?

Speaker 2

What tools do you use? So I'm not directly responsible for the vetting of the dependencies, but on a more personal level, if I see there are some dependencies that are widely used. So that's what I check how widely used a dependence is.

If you get it on Marven, it also shows the number of downloads and their reviews on dependencies. And like recently I was working with the, there's a dependence for PDFs that I was, that was on the project. It's always been working. But when I wanted to upgrade, I realized it was way, way, way out of date.

I tried to update it. Then, you know, when they update a plugin or a dependency, they write what's new in that with that plugin. So I looked at the things that they were changing. Then I realized there were some security issues that they were addressing.

But then for me, that automatically meant the lower version had those security vulnerabilities. But to upgrade to the new one, it was almost an impossible task because there were a lot of changes and we didn't need to reimplement the whole item. Hence, we had two options to keep using the old one because it works, but it has security vulnerabilities or use another one which is widely used.

So I ended up opting for completely ditching that piece of dependence and using a new one which is widely trusted and it's got a lot of developers on it. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. So when you are deciding to update to newer versions, you consider whether it can be updated quickly without any breaking changes or.

Speaker 2

Yes yes yes yeah yeah um so when you um the depending on the changes that they're talking about or the new updates they are minor updates sometimes they are minor updates but they are major updates at some points uh that you'd need the implementation would now be different

Yeah, for example, if it was if it was `.trim()`. it's now `.cut()`. So you have got to go and find in the code everywhere where you implemented dot trim to dot dot cut. So you've got to change those. But some of it there will be major, major changes that can break the whole system.

You might need months to implement the new items. For example, in spring, changing from spring 2 to spring 3 point something, something version, there's a lot of changes on the implementation.

So on updates, whatever updates that are coming in, sometimes they might come with a different implementation and it will definitely break the system. So you need to redo it and retest everything and make sure it's not fixed.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. I'm interested in knowing, are there any tools that you use to scan your dependencies to see whether they have some security issues or Or maybe there's another team at the end of that.

Speaker 2

Good question. We scan dependencies. But in spring, there's-- OK, quickly, let me just quickly check here. I'm quickly checking my code. What is it called? It's I think it's component scan, yes. So Spring itself has got a mechanism to scan the dependencies.

So there's a, we call it, it's dependent injection anyway. So within Spring, so it's called component scan. So it's a, what do you call it? The annotation that you use, it's called component scan. So it's just, it just happens under the hood with spring.

Just put it, then spring does the whole thing. Also, we also make use of SonarQube. So SonarQube, scans the whole code. So when it sees things that are not they're not really good. It it notifies you. and it fails depending on the rules that have been put. So there is also a team which works on those rules.

Speaker 1

Alright. Thank you for that. And okay, so I'm not really very familiar with spring. How does spring on its own rely on many dependencies Or is it a purchase included framework way? If you install spring, you don't have to install so many dependencies.

Speaker 2

So the dependencies depend on what you are using. I mean on on the functionality that you need. So spring is a framework that allows you to. Okay, when we go to the frameworks, first, we've got the normal programming language, for example, Java.

Speaker 1

Yes.

Speaker 2

You're writing your code in Java, right? Or in Python. Then there's a lot of boilerplate code that you write within that programming language. So when you incorporate the uh the framework for example spring now you no longer have to write everything down if to declare a uh a class you would if you used to say uh class student is equal to new class so that you can now use the you know the

Hey, I don't know what's happening with my vocabulary today, but yeah, as... Okay, for example, if you want to declare a student, you say student, student equal to new student. Now you're trying to create an object of that item. But now if you're using Spring, you just inject all the objects of that class.

You don't really have to declare it like that. So that's what mainly does. It saves you to write from writing a lot of code. It just injects stuff, scans all your code, then injects give you the items or the objects that you need.

And also the things like component scanning, the one that I just told you about, scanning all the packages and subpackages, it helps you with that. instead of you doing it manually in the code. So that's what it means. Then the other external dependence that you need, does those have to do with your specific task.

For example, if you want to print PDF files, you have to have a dependence for that. And that is not in Spring, that's in another. dependencies that depends external dependence that you would need.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. And then so in with open source dependencies, it's common for creators of packages to abandon their projects.

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

Yes. So how do you check where the project is still being maintained? If it is the dependence in your project.

Speaker 2

A good question. That is the issue that I mentioned in the beginning about the or that item. So that's a weakness in big systems. because usually, if it's working. or just don't try to fix it. like a a vulnerability that I've mentioned that dependence is outdated. and it has got security issues. but it has not been updated in the last 4 years. It's still like that. So that's difficult. That's the challenge that we have that's need to be addressed, probably. But I would say it falls on the developer, or maybe the lead. Yes, they call it checked it. So the lead job is supposed to be taken care of detected. He has to go through the projects to see what we have and what up to date. So, and they have to keep it like we have tech debt of this and this.

But sometimes tech debt keep piling up because, like I said, to upgrade from two to three is massive amounts of work and a lot of disruption. And if it's working at this moment, it's not as, it might not be treated as a very urgent issue until we start receiving the attacks. So those things are usually set aside. They just go little by little while the project is advancing.

There are more new features, new bugs being sold. Those are priority at this moment than tech debt, which is not, it's a debatable issue. But the tech lead or the team lead or the lead developer, in our case, the lead developer should be responsible or is the one who is responsible for managing detected?

Speaker 1

And, okay, usually how long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your projects? I know that might vary depending on the complexity.

Speaker 2

Yeah, so yeah, that varies depending on the project. on how big the project is. I work on quite a very big, one of the biggest projects in the, if it's not the biggest, in the organization. There are so many other projects. I think there are over 50 projects.

The one that I work on is one of the biggest, if it's not the biggest. So it becomes a problem because there are many teams. Within our project, there are squads, different squads. because because of it being a microservice architecture.

So some work on these other other part of the platform, different parts of the platform. So in terms of trying to do the proper, you know, what is it called the release process? Yeah. continuous development, CI/CD, it doesn't really come, it's a challenge because you cannot just sort out code today and update the, you know, the plugin and tomorrow it's online.

You cannot just do that. After you make an update, someone You've got to test it through the different environments. Then we've got testers. We've got to do a clarity testing to make sure that the system is broken and that's working. Then you wait for your release day.

There are specific release days. I think it's some day, okay, I won't mention the day, but there's a certain day of the week where releases are, when releases are done. So for instance, if we are to say every month, we only do releases on Monday. That means whatever happens on Tuesday, we wait for Monday to introduce it.

But even if we're waiting for Monday, my team might not be the one which is releasing on Monday. So I'll wait for my turn probably after a month.

Speaker 1

Oh, yeah.

Speaker 2

So which is an issue for bigger systems. But that also depends on how urgent the issue is. If it's a very urgent issue and there's a serious vulnerability that is there that has been discovered that needs to be addressed, then obviously desperate solutions code for

Speaker 1

So in other communities, for example, in Python, if a dependence is widely used and it's no longer being maintained, community members may step up to take over the maintenance, or sometimes some companies take over the maintenance of dependencies.

Speaker 1

Is this something that happens within the spring community to take over dependency, to maintain it? For example, within your organization, would you take up the maintenance of a dependence that you are using? so that it continues to be maintained. And how easy is that to do?

Speaker 2

That won't be easy, because for the open. Okay, I'll if it's if it's if it's already open source. and you can do that if you see if it's if it's already open source, you can do that, but not necessarily representing the organization doing that. It's just something that you're doing for that that you're doing for fun. So you find that on on some dependencies.

Someone is doing that already. Yeah, so you can just use those ones. But whenever you are using the one that is updated, that is, you have to make sure that it's your responsibility. If you're choosing any dependencies, it's your responsibility to make sure that it's it's safe. But that's but when we are not generally in a habit of picking up unmaintained plugins.

And because we're already busy with ourselves, anyway.

Speaker 1

Okay, you know, it's it's not that you're picking it up. You were already using it, and it's no longer being in there. So.

Speaker 2

Yes, it makes sense just that sometimes there is something already ready to use. And because you're you're now giving yourself some work work on that item the project on its own. Because if it's there, it exists and it's widely used. That means someone is taking time, someone goes to work for that thing.

Speaker 1

No, but as someone who's active in the open source community, I mean, I know that there are many dependencies that don't have, that are being maintained by volunteers. And those projects don't have funding to pay people to maintain them. This is why we have a lot of dependencies ending up unmaintained.

Speaker 2

Okay.

Speaker 1

And which creates a problem when people relying on that dependency and it becomes unmaintained and just some security vulnerabilities and people need to use it.

Speaker 2

All right. All right. Maybe it's a personal thing. I might not find time for that. All right. But I understand some of the things, someone is doing that in some dependency that that person is just not me. Maybe some colleagues are doing that. Some of my colleagues are doing that. But yeah.

Speaker 1

No, you haven't. And what, okay, what practices and tools are in place for supply and chain and tax mitigation in your projects?

Speaker 2

Chain attacks.

Speaker 1

Supply chain attacks, like what practices and tools are in place for mitigate supply chain attacks within your project.

Speaker 2

Okay, by supplying chain attacks, you...

Speaker 1

Okay, what I mean is supply the way a supply chain attack usually happens is there's a dependency that you are using. It may happen that some developers may inject malicious code into it. When you update your dependencies like you do, uh they can launch an attack within your project but the project now the attack now won't be limited to uh your own project it might if there are people who are also rely on your project like they rely on

dependencies that you have built uh it means or it goes upstream and it attacks those uh those systems that rely on your project okay yes so I'm asking if there are any tools and practices you have in place to ensure that supply chain attacks are not launched through dependencies within your project.

Speaker 2

Okay. One second. I'm just trying to check some of the stuff that we have in the playbook. So, all right. Okay, so the first thing that we have, I think what I've been working on, what I have done is, on the project that I'm working on, we've been using tools like SonarQube.

So SonarQube, we use SonarQube, it scans the whole code, scans the dependencies, scans everything to look for those vulnerabilities. And when you push code, it won't be merged into the main repository until those things are maintained, I mean, are fixed. Then also yeah, we also do a OWASP Dependency Check.

I don't know if yeah. yeah, the the all the OWASP Dependency Check. I'm actually studying for, for the OWASP exam. Oh, okay. At the moment. So yeah, mainly that's what mainly used that I can remember. It's just the playbook is big. So, yeah, but, oh, also, hmm. Oh, yeah.

So there's a UK government's software security code of conduct. So you try to follow that whenever we're using those new tools, because security is quite a big thing. If you don't know if you remember, around 2015 or 2016, there was a huge attack on the UK government's NHS system. And it paralyzed, almost paralyzed the whole of NHS. So people have got everyone who is involved in a public entity, we've got to use the UK government's software security code of practice. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And have any of your projects ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

Hmm. Not, okay, not the projects that I'm working on, but we have been made aware of an attack that was going, that was doing rounds, you know, something like, when there's a ransomware that you remember the time, if you remember the time where ransomware is just were doing their thing.

Yeah. So stuff like that. There was a recent attack on processing attack on every on all the software systems anyway. It's called the I think Shai-Hulud or something like that.

Speaker 1

Okay.

Speaker 2

Yeah. So the Shai-Hulud it didn't get to attack us. But it was it was going to attack us eventually, if we're not, if if we didn't if we're not on the lookout for those of opposite stuff. Is it good? Yeah. You sent me a spelling of. Yeah, I'm I'm trying to look for the for the actual spelling.

Speaker 1

So I can look it up.

Speaker 2

Yeah, so I'll I'll I'll send you the spelling for the.

Speaker 1

Alright, thank you. And are there any what factors help you to address vulnerabilities within your projects?

Speaker 2

Sorry, can you hear me again?

Speaker 1

What factors are favorable or help you to address vulnerabilities within your projects? Or maybe the opposite would be, what challenges do you face? Which hinder you in addressing vulnerability, vulnerable defenders within your project? Oh yeah, so the- What works and what hinders?

Speaker 2

Okay. So there's a challenge that we, the project is big and there's so much work to do. So, and so many, that means so many dependencies per each and every microservice. So it becomes a challenge to keep yourself up to date with every dependency. However, to address that, that's one of the major roles of the team lead, to look out for those vulnerabilities. So there is is so the team lead it being his role to look out for that is the one who makes sure that dependents up to date.

We are following this those rules and also the team which updates the rules in the sonar cube. So yeah, I think that's how that's what we look at. That's that's how we try and mitigate the challenges.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And do you have any recommendations for other developers on dependent management so that they can be able to mitigate a supply chain attack based on your experience?

Speaker 2

I would say, okay, other than just keeping up to date with what's happening in the tech trends, because usually when there's something, it's reported and people talk about it and there are ways to sort that out. I think keeping your dependencies up to date. It's very critical and trying to solve your tactic as soon as possible.

That's also critical. And there should be always be. So keep your keep your code up to date. Keep your dependence up to date and do the like. I mentioned that we have the problem that our releases take longer. If you try and find a way to make sure that it's a real continuous development and continuous integration, that means that allows continuous, you know, updating of your items and making use of the tools like the SonarQube.

I found that very useful. If possible, resources being available. put someone in charge of making sure that that everything is up to date. Yeah, that's what I can say.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you so much. I think that's all for me. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

No problem.

Speaker 1

I'll stop recording now.